

COMPARISON OF EXPLICIT RUNGE-KUTTA METHODS WITH HYBRID METHODS OF MULTI-STEP TYPE

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Abstract

As is known, in solving some of applied problems, Runge-Kutta methods are used, considering that these methods are explicit and do not require the use of any other methods. Note that, like other methods, the Runge-Kutta methods also have their own advantages and disadvantages. One of the main disadvantages of Runge-Kutta method consists of repeatedly calculating the function $f(x, y)$, which is right-hand side of the differential equation, and one of the advantages of Runge-Kutta methods is that they are one step methods. Usually, such methods are considered as the recurrent relationships. A well-known representative of the Runge-Kutta method is the Euler and Midpoint methods. It is known that one of the exact methods is called the hybrid method, which can be taken as the generalization of the Midpoint method. Consequently, the Runge-Kutta and Hybrid methods are generalizations of this method. By using this, here we consider the comparison of some specific Runge-Kutta methods with the corresponding hybrid methods. Since implicit hybrid methods are more exact, it becomes necessary to compare hybrid methods with the semi-implicit Runge-Kutta methods. By considering a specific method, we compare semi-implicit Runge-Kutta methods with implicit hybrid methods.

Keywords: Initial-value problem, Runge-Kutta methods, Stability and Degree, Hybrid methods, Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs).

Introduction. The Runge-Kutta methods are constructed for solving following problem:

$$y' = f(x, y), \quad y(x_0) = y_0, \quad x_0 \leq x \leq X, \quad (1)$$

which is called the initial-value problem for ODEs.

Here, suppose that the problem (1) has a unique continuous solution $y(x)$, which is defined in the segment $[x_0, X]$ and has derivatives up to $p + 1$, inclusively. And the continuity of the function $f(x, y)$ with respect to all arguments is assumed, and it is defined in some closed set. Assume that the function $f(x, y)$ has partial derivatives up to p , inclusively.

To find the numerical solution of the problem (1), let us denote by $y(x_i)$ - the exact values of the solution of problem (1) of the mesh point x_i , and the corresponding approximated values by y_i ($i = 0, 1, \dots, N$). The mesh point x_{i+1} is defined by the equality $x_{i+1} = x_i + h$, where $0 < h$ - is the step-size. For the value of the function $f(x, y)$ at the mesh point x_i , let us use notation $f_i = f_i(x_i, y_i)$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, N$) for the approximated values, and $f(x_i, y(x_i))$ for the exact values at the point x_i , $i = 0, 1, \dots, N$.

The problem has been studied by many scientists, starting with Newton, using the task of solving problem (1) with the help of a definite integral. It is noted that, in this case, for calculating the integral, one can use the Newton-Cotes method. The first direct method for solving the initial-value problem for ODEs of the first-order was constructed by Euler, which is still being used successfully. A more general numerical method for solving problem (1) was constructed by Adams, which has been generalized by many authors and is presented as follows:

$$\sum_{i=0}^k \alpha_i y_{n+i} = h \sum_{i=0}^k \beta_i f_{n+i}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N - k, \quad (2)$$

here, the coefficients α_i, β_i ($i = 0, 1, \dots, k$) are real numbers, and $\alpha_k \neq 0$. Method (2) was fundamentally investigated by Dahlquist. It is noted that the Runge-Kutta method was developed by J. Butcher, leading to the construction of the semi-implicit and implicit Runge-Kutta methods (as is known, the classical Runge-Kutta methods are explicit). Thus, receive that Runge-Kutta methods can be used in three forms. Explicit Runge-Kutta methods were constructed by Runge and Kutta, and they have been well-studied by later researchers. Therefore, let us consider the semi-implicit Runge-Kutta method, which can be presented as follows:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + h(l_1 K_1^{(n)} + l_2 K_2^{(n)} + \dots + l_s K_s^{(n)}), \quad (3)$$

here,

$$K_1^{(n)} = f(x_n + \alpha_1 h, y_n + h\beta_{1,1} K_1^{(n)}), \quad K_2^{(n)} = f(x_n + \alpha_2 h, y_n + h(\beta_{2,1} K_1^{(n)} + \beta_{2,2} K_2^{(n)})), \quad \dots, \\ K_s^{(n)} = f(x_n + \alpha_s h, y_n + h(\beta_{s,1} K_1^{(n)} + \beta_{s,2} K_2^{(n)} + \dots + \beta_{s,s} K_s^{(n)})).$$

All the quantities $K_i^{(n)} (i = 1, 2, \dots, s)$ are defined by the solution of nonlinear algebraic equations, which makes the application of method (3) more difficult. Note that if, in method (3), we set $\beta_{i,i} = 0 (i = 1, 2, \dots, s)$, then method (3) reduces to the explicit Runge-Kutta method. Method (3) is more exact than explicit Runge-Kutta methods. As is commonly known, stable methods are usually compared with high degree methods. Note that the concept of order of accuracy for method (2) is referred to as the degree, because k represents the order of the finite-difference method (2). Method (3) is always stable. The numerical methods constructed to solve problem (1) have been studied by many authors (see for example, [1]-[20]).

But in the application of the method (3), the necessity arises for multiple calculations of the function $f(x, y)$ at each step. However, for the application of method (2), it is only necessary to calculate $f(x, y)$ once or twice. Taking into account the above-described comparison, experts mainly proposed using methods of type (2). Some specialists believe that method (2) is a generalization of well-known methods such as Euler's methods, the Trapezoid method, the Simpson's method, etc. There are many papers dedicated to comparing the Multistep Method with the Runge-Kutta methods. Usually, method (2) is investigated with the help of concepts "stability" and "degree", which can be defined as follows:

Definition 1. Method (2) is called stable if the roots of the following polynomial:

$$\rho(\lambda) = \alpha_k \lambda^k + \alpha_{k-1} \lambda^{k-1} + \dots + \alpha_1 \lambda + \alpha_0$$

are located inside the unit circle, and on the boundary of the unit circle, there are no multiple roots.

Definition 2. The integer value p is called the degree of method (2), if the following holds:

$$\sum_{i=0}^k (\alpha_i y(x+ih) - h(\beta_i y'(x+ih))) = O(h^{p+1}), h \rightarrow 0 .$$

Dahlquist proved the following theorem:

Theorem. Suppose that method (2) has the degree p . Then, in the class of methods (2), there exists a method with degree of $p = 2k$, which is unique. If method (2) has the degree p and is stable, then there exist stable methods with the degree:

$$p \leq 2[k/2] + 2$$

for implicit methods, and

$$p \leq k$$

for explicit methods. There are methods with degree p_{\max} for each k .

Often, there arises a necessity for constructing stable numerical methods with degree $p \leq 2[k/2] + 2$. Some authors have suggested using the following method:

$$\sum_{i=0}^k \alpha_i y_{n+i} = h \sum_{i=0}^k \beta_i f_{n+i+v_i}, \quad |v_i| < 1, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N - k, \tag{4}$$

which is called the hybrid method. A well-known representative of this method is the Midpoint method. As is known, this method is explicit, stable, and has the degree $p = 2$. It is clear that this method has both positive and negative properties. The academician Yanenko also studied similar methods, which he referred to as fractional methods.

§1. Comparison of the Multistep Method (2) with the Hybrid method (4)

To compare the above methods (2) and (4), let us consider a specific case $k = 1$. In this case, the method with p_{\max} derived from methods (2) and (4) for the $k = 1$ can be presented as follows:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + h(f_n + f_{n+1})/2, \tag{5}$$

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + hf(x_n + h/2, y_{n+1/2}). \tag{6}$$

It is easy to understand that for the construction of method two mesh-points have been used, but for the construction method (6), three points have been used. Method (5) has the degree $p = 2$ and method (6) also has the degree $p = 2$. As noted above, method (6) can be received from the Runge-Kutta method. If, in method (6), h is changed by $2h$, then obtain:

$$y_{n+2} = y_n + 2hf_{n+1}, \tag{7}$$

which can be received from method (2) as a partial case. Note that for receiving method (7) from method (2), it is enough to put $k = 2$ in method (2).

According to Dahlquist's theorem, in the class of methods (2), there exists a stable method with the degree $p = 2$ for the $k = 2$. If we take into account that in method (4), the amount of unknowns is equal to $3k + 3$, then we include that method (4) allows for the construction of more accurate methods.

For the demonstration of the advantages of methods of type (4), let us consider the following method:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + h(f_{n+1/2+\alpha} + f_{n+1/2-\alpha})/2, \quad \alpha = \sqrt{3}/6. \quad (8)$$

Method (8) is received from method (4) as a partial case for the value $k = 1$. Note that method (8) is stable and has the degree $p = 4$. Method (6) and (8) are partial cases of method (4). In method (6), hybrid mesh-point have been used, which is a rational number, whereas in method (8), an irrational number has been used, because these methods have different properties. As is known, a method is considered given if the number of points ($k + 1$ mesh-points) used for its construction is known. If the values of k - are given, then by solving the following,

$$\sum_{i=0}^k \alpha_i = 0; \quad \sum_{i=0}^k \beta_i = \sum_{i=0}^k i \alpha_i; \quad \sum_{i=0}^k l_i \beta_i = \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{i^2}{2!} \alpha_i; \quad \dots; \quad \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{l_i^{p-1}}{(p-1)!} \beta_i = \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{i^p}{p!} \alpha_i \quad (9)$$

here, $l_i = i + \nu_i$; $i = 0, 1, \dots, k$.

Note that the ratio (9) is a nonlinear system of algebraic equations; therefore, finding the solution of this system is not always possible. This system reminds us of the system of algebraic equations used in the construction of known Gauss methods for calculating definite integrals.

In method (4), $3k + 3$ coefficients participate. Therefore, in system of (9), there are $3k + 3$ unknowns and $p + 1$ equations. The system of algebraic equations (9) is homogeneous, which always has the trivial solution, but this is of no interest. Using this citation, some authors assume that $\alpha_k \neq 0$, because y_{n+k} - is the solution of equation (4). This follows from the fact that method (4) can be taken as an k -step method. As is known, method (4) can be applied to solve some problems if the values y_0, y_1, \dots, y_{k-1} are known.

By using the condition of $\alpha_k \neq 0$, receive that in system (9), there are $3k + 2$ unknowns and $p + 1$ equations. If this system has a solution, then it must satisfy $p + 1 \leq 3k + 2$ or $p \leq 3k + 1$. In the case $k = 1$, by solving the nonlinear algebraic system (9), one can construct different methods. In this case, method with the p_{\max} - is method (8). If we require that the values of the parameters α - be rational number, then $p_{\max} \leq 3$ will take place. For example, the following method:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + h(f_n + 3f_{n+2/3})/4, \quad (10)$$

is stable, has the degree $p = 3$. In the case $k = 2$, from method (4), one can receive the following method:

$$y_{n+2} = y_{n+1} + h(5f_{n+3/2+\beta} + 8f_{n+3/2} + 5f_{n+3/2-\beta})/18, \quad \beta = \sqrt{15}/10. \quad (11)$$

This method is stable and has the degree $p = 6$. As was shown above, $p_{\max} = 3k + 1$. Consequently, for $k = 2$, receive that $p_{\max} = 7$. Note that methods with degree $p_{\max} = 3k + 1$ are unstable. However, method (11) is stable; therefore, the degree for method (11) is less than p_{\max} .

Let us define p_{\max} for stable methods of type (4). To do this, consider the following theorem:

Theorem 2. If method (4) is stable and has the degree of p , then $p \leq 2k + 2$, and there exist stable methods with degree $p = 2k + 2$ for each k .

Methods (10) and (11) are subject to the results of Theorem 2.

Note that the stable method (10) has been constructed for the value $k = 1$. By using the above-mentioned rule, receive that method (8) is unique. It follows that $p_{\max} = 2k + 2$ for the $k = 1$, and in this case, $3k + 1 = 2k + 2$ if $k = 1$.

Now, let us consider the application of hybrid methods to solve problem (1). As was noted above, all hybrid-type methods can be considered explicit. However, at each step, it becomes necessary to calculate the values of the solution at hybrid points. For example, in the application of method (8), the values $y_{n+1/2\pm\alpha}$ must be known. V.Ibrahimov has constructed methods for calculating the values $y_{n+1/2\pm\alpha}$. Additionally, he has defined some approaches for constructing similar methods.

Here, it has been shown that some disadvantages of hybrid methods can be eliminated by using predictor-corrector methods. To illustrate this, let us consider the following method:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + h(f_{n+1} + 3f_{n+1/3})/4. \quad (12)$$

This method is similar to method (10). Note that method (12) is implicit, whereas method (10) is explicit. Using these, one can construct the following predictor-corrector methods:

$$\hat{y}_{n+1} = y_n + h(f(x_n, y_n) + 3f(x_n + 2h/3))/4, \quad (13)$$

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + h(f(x_n + h, \hat{y}_{n+1}) + 3f(x_n + 2h/3, y_{n+2/3}))/4. \quad (14)$$

In these cases, the midpoint method can be used as the predictor method.

Conclusion: This work has demonstrated both the advantages and disadvantages of hybrid methods. Additionally, an attempt has been made to show that the disadvantages of hybrid methods can be eliminated by using predictor-corrector methods, as given in (13) and (14). By comparing methods (13) and (14) with the Runge-Kutta methods (3) and (4), one can observe that these methods are very similar in appearance. Furthermore, a comparison reveals that these methods have intersecting areas. To illustrate this, the values of the function participated in the hybrid methods can be defined using the notation from method (2) or (3). In solving many practical problems, the question arises of determining the availability of the obtained results. For this purpose, the predictor-corrector method can be used. However, the bilateral method for a precise determination of the availability of results. Methods (10) and (12) can be taken as the bilateral methods.

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